

Influence of Utilization of Electronic Instructional Media on Undergraduate Educational Management Students' Academic Performance in Rivers State Universities

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Abstract

The study investigated influence of utilization of electronic instructional media on undergraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities. Six specific objectives, six research questions and six hypotheses guided the study. This study adopted quasi-experimental research design. The population of the study was all 170 level 300 undergraduate Educational Management students in Rivers State Universities. The study used the entire population. The data collecting instrument for this study is a self-structured questionnaire titled "Influence of Utilization of Electronic Instructional Media on Undergraduate Educational Management Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire." The instrument was structured using 4-point rating scale and was face and content validated by the researcher's supervisor and two experts in Measurement and Evaluation in Rivers State University. The instrument was tested for reliability using test-retest reliability technique and the scores collated were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient which yielded an average reliability index of 0.77. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using quasi-experimental design at 0.05 level of significance with a critical value of ± 1.96 . Findings revealed that lecturers' utilization of zoom, google classroom, WhatsApp, digital textbooks, open educational resources, and computer networks in instructional delivery influences students' academic performance in Rivers State universities to a high extent. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that seminars and training workshops be regularly organized to empower the teachers with skills needed for using the zoom for instructional delivery by the school management.

Keywords: *Utilization, Electronic media, instruction, undergraduate, academic performance.*

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Introduction

It is an established fact that universities are institutions for the impartation of knowledge, skills and attitudes that are profitable to not only students but the society at large. As institutions of higher learning, universities continuously build on the knowledge, skills, values and attitudes learnt at the lower levels of education to make citizens live and function as productive members of the society, earning a living and contributing to societal progress (Abali, 2018). The 1959 Ashby Commission on post-secondary education prescribed university education as a tool for achieving national development, economic expansion and social emancipation of individuals. Also, the 1990 Longe Commission on the review of higher education in Nigeria identified university education as the most powerful instrument for social reform. It is, therefore, the expectations of Nigerians that universities are sources of intellectual power that can be mobilized for the socio-economic development of the nation (Ibadin, 2011).

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Students are beneficiaries of university education all over the world. Therefore, the expectations of societies that universities offer citizens functional education that enhances students' performance as well as assist them contribute meaningfully to development of the society. Thus, for a nation to arise and become worthy to compete favourably in the confederation of nations, it must ensure that the students perform excellently in their various academic disciplines. To achieve this, higher institutions such as universities must maintain and retain high quality teaching and learning which will consequently lead to the attainment of high academic performance among students. Academic performance is the pillar of education. It is an issue of public concern as it affects students, teachers, school administrators, parents and governments.

A student's academic performance in an examination is dependent on his cumulative grade point average. This assertion is supported by Entwistle and Wilson in Festus and Andre (2014) that a student's success is generally judged by examination performance while the best criterion of performance is the sum of the student's academic performance in all the courses taken. The achievement of high academic performance is the ultimate goal of every student and the main purpose of qualitative education. The poor academic performance will invariably affect the students, teachers, the parents, and the society at large.

Technology integration into students' instruction gave rise to electronic instructional media as a concept. Since in the 1990s, because of advances in technology and in theories of learning and cognition, electronic instructional media has taken more different forms, and the kinds of learning that has been used to promote it have expanded significantly. Electronic instructional media brings about positive outcome and enhances retention if properly integrated. It encourages cooperation and collaboration among peers in the same class. It provides courage over one another and offers learners flexible teaching and learning environment. In electronic instructional media usage, technology is used to serve multiple learning styles or needs, engage learners, prepare students for life after school, and bring the brick-and-mortar classroom into the 21st century. Some of the electronic instructional media that are discussed as identified in this study include zoom app and computer networks.

Zoom cloud-based service is a video-chatting tool that can be used to hold online classrooms and even participate in online presentations. The free version of zoom offers a number of helpful features for lecturers, such as the ability to conduct meetings with up to 100 participants, and to allow students to wordlessly signal to the lecturer that they have a question, brainstorm on a virtual whiteboard, and collaborate on projects by annotating documents on other students' screens. Zoom is an electronic instruction medium that is changing the world we live in and the way we teach and learn. Zoom is the leader in modern enterprise video communications, with an easy, reliable cloud platform for video and audio conferencing, collaboration, chat, and webinars across mobile devices, desktops, telephones, and room systems. Oliveira (2013) affirmed that zoom technology has grown in popularity due to its benefits such as, being able to send real-time messages to an individual or groups of friends simultaneously, low cost, and privacy. Zoom applications have potential to improve teaching, learners being active in their studies, interaction between students on personal, school, and course related topics (Smit, 2012).

A computer network is a group of interconnected nodes or computing devices that exchange data and resources with each other. A network connection between these devices can be established using cable or wireless media. Once a connection is established, communication protocols such as simple mail transfer protocol and hypertext transfer protocol are used to exchange data between the network devices. A computer network can be as small as two laptops connected through an ethernet cable or as complex as the internet, which is a global system of computer networks (Izenshark & Leahy, 2015).

Students' interest and academic performance are dependent on a variety of factors and stand out to reveal how well courses are being taught in institutions of learning. Elenwo and Ebom-Jebose (2023) opined that academic performance is the extent to which a student has attained his short or long-term educational goals. It is the learning outcomes of the student which includes the knowledge, skills and ideas acquired and obtained through their course of study within and outside the classroom situation. Presently, utilization of the electronic instructional media can facilitate not only the delivery of instruction, but also the quality of learning attained by students. Hence, Agabi and Okorie (2012) averred that students'

cognitive and manipulative performance become more positive after being exposed to electronic instructional media. The utilization of these media in teaching and learning is essential, mostly when the expected results have not been achieved in students' performance in examinations. Researchers such as Akbas and Pektus (2021) have shown that most teachers adopt conventional teaching methods which are teacher centered and subsequently result in poor learning outcomes. This brings to limelight the need to investigate the influence of utilization of electronic instructional media on undergraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities.

Statement of the Problem

Since the internet revolution, there has been a shift in learning due to the development of internet, use of educative online platforms, digital devices, among others. This had led to a dramatic instructional innovative change from traditional to technological pedagogy by lecturers in Nigerian universities, and in effect the introduction of various innovative digital technologies. Therefore, lecturers need to upgrade in facilities that require value added skills in teaching with the use of electronic instructional media such as zoom, google classroom, WhatsApp, digital textbooks, open educational resources among others. Unfortunately, some authors (Ekici (2017), Pardede (2019) and Kamanetz, (2020) have expressed worry over low availability (inadequacy) of ICT tools for effective instructional delivery in most educational institutions. A focused group discussion with some teachers by the researcher during the study revealed that they sometimes not made use of computer sets and other ICT facilities in delivery of instruction due to either non-availability or non-functionality of the available ICT facilities and poor knowledge on the use of such ICT tools. Azih (2011) reported that many factors could challenge the utilization of ICT in the learning environment. For instance, Okoli, Ohaegbulam and Oladunjoye (2015) decried insufficient computer laboratories in schools, erratic power supply, and absence of internet, limited computer facilities for teachers, no central databases, and no learning management systems available for the purposes of electronic learning. The authors further pointed out insufficient capacity building and training for the teachers who ought to have been provided with sufficient training on how to use such facilities when provided. These identified problems, therefore, have informed the researcher to conduct a study on the influence of utilization of electronic instructional media on undergraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the influence of utilization of electronic instructional media on undergraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities. Specifically, the objectives are to:

1. Find out the influence of utilization of zoom in instructional delivery on undergraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities.
2. Ascertain the influence of utilization of computer networks in instructional delivery on undergraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities.

Research Questions

The following research questions was answered in this study:

1. what is the influence of utilization of zoom in instructional delivery on undergraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities?
2. What is the influence of utilization of computer networks in instructional delivery on undergraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested in this study at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean performance of students of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the influence of utilization of zoom in instructional

delivery on undergraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities.

2. There is no significant difference in the mean performance of students of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the influence of utilization of computer networks in instructional delivery on undergraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities.

Methodology

The research adopted a quasi-experimental research design. The study was conducted in Rivers State. The population of the study was one hundred and seventy (170) respondents comprising of 64 and 106 Undergraduate Educational Management students in the two public Rivers State Universities namely the Rivers State University (RSU) and the Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. The study used the entire population of the students as it was manageable in size. The research developed two instruments each for research questions 1-6 having 20 multiple choice questions each with option A-D for the study. These instruments were Utilization of Electronic Instructional Media Achievement Test (UEIMAT) and Undergraduate Educational Management Students Achievement Test (UEMSAT) which were used to determine influence of utilization of electronic instructional media on undergraduate educational management students' academic performance in Rivers State Universities. The questionnaire was given to the researchers' supervisor and two other experts in measurement and evaluation to ascertain the face and content validity of the instrument. The purpose of the study and the research questions were also made available to them at the time of validation. The reliability of the instruments was established by a trial test which was carried out by the researcher. The test re-test reliability technique was used to ascertain the reliability of the instruments. The instruments were pilot tested on 20 students selected from the University of Port Harcourt which is outside the universities understudy. The scores collated were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) and the reliability coefficient of 0.77 was realized. The researcher administered 284 copies of the questionnaire to the respondents (284 students) with the help of three research assistants. All the copies were successfully retrieved and used for data analysis. Data collected for the purpose of this study was analyzed using mean and standard deviation and z-Test statistical tool to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. A null hypothesis will be accepted when the calculated z-value is less than the critical z-value of ± 1.96 and rejected when the calculated z-value is greater than the critical z-value of ± 1.96 respectively.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the influence of utilization of zoom in instructional delivery on undergraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities?

Table 1. Mean of Pretest and Posttest Scores of Treatment and Control Groups Taught Using Zoom in Instructional Delivery and Conventional Teaching Method

Group	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Difference	Mean Gain
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD		
Experimental	64	45.15	3.16	73.08	2.97	27.93	10.47
Control	106	44.15	3.06	61.61	2.68	17.46	

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2024.

The results in Table 4.1 shows that the experimental group taught using zoom in instructional delivery had a mean score of 45.15 in the pre-test and a mean score of 73.08 in the post-test making a pretest, posttest mean difference of 27.93. The nonexperimental/control group taught using conventional teaching method had a mean score of 44.15 in the pretest and a posttest mean of 61.61 with a pretest posttest mean difference of 17.46. This, however, gave rise to mean gain of 10.47 for the class. With this results, undergraduate Educational Management students taught using zoom in instructional delivery had a higher mean performance score than those taught using conventional technique in the utilization of electronic instructional media achievement test (UEIMAT).

Research Question 2

To what extent does utilization of computer networks in instructional delivery influence undergraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities?

Table 2. Mean of Pre-test and Post-test Scores of Treatment and Control Groups Taught Using Computer Networks in Instructional Delivery and Conventional Teaching Method

Group	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Difference	Mean Gain
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD		
Experimental	64	21.33	5.54	38.37	8.73	17.04	5.36
Control	106	19.56	4.36	31.24	6.42	11.68	

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2024.

The results in Table 2 shows that the experimental group taught using computer networks in instructional delivery had a mean score of 38.37 in the pre-test and a mean score of 21.33 in the post-test making a pre-test, post-test mean difference of 17.04. The nonexperimental/control group taught using conventional teaching method had a mean score of 31.24 in the pre-test and a post-test mean of 19.56 with a pre-test post-test mean difference of 11.68. This, however, gave rise to mean gain of 5.36 for the class. With this result, it was deduced that undergraduate Educational Management students taught using computer networks in instructional delivery perform better than those taught using conventional technique in the utilization of electronic instructional media achievement test (UEIMAT).

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of students of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the influence of utilization of zoom in instructional delivery on undergraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities.

Table 3. z-Test Analysis for Mean Performance Scores of Students Taught Using Zoom in Instructional Delivery and those Taught with Conventional Approach

Groups	N	Mean	SD	Df	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Experimental	64	73.08	2.97	168	24.93	± 1.96	Reject
Control	106	61.61	2.68				

The analyzed data in Table 3 showed that the z-cal was 24.93 while the critical table value was ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and 168 degree of freedom. Since the z-cal is greater than the z-crit, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of students of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the influence of utilization of zoom in instructional delivery on undergraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in

Rivers State universities was rejected. The alternate hypothesis was therefore, accepted indicating that there is a significant difference in the mean performance scores of the experimental group taught using zoom in instructional delivery and those nonexperimental/control group taught using conventional teaching method.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of students of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the influence of utilization of computer networks in instructional delivery on undergraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities.

Table 4. z-Test Analysis for Mean Performance Scores of Students Taught Using Computer Networks in Instructional Delivery and those Taught with Conventional Approach

Groups	N	Mean	SD	Df	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Experimental	64	38.37	8.73	168	5.66	±1.96	Reject
Control	106	31.24	6.42				

The analysed data in Table 4 showed that the z-cal was 5.66 while the critical table value was ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and 168 degree of freedom. Since the z-cal is greater than the z-crit, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of students of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the influence of utilization of computer networks in instructional delivery on undergraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities was rejected. The alternate hypothesis was therefore, accepted indicating that there is a significant difference in the mean performance scores of the experimental group taught using computer networks in instructional delivery and the nonexperimental/control group taught using conventional teaching method.

Discussion of the Findings

The data presented Table 3 determined the difference in the academic performance of undergraduate Educational Management students in Rivers State universities taught using zoom in instructional delivery and the nonexperimental/control group taught using conventional teaching method. The finding revealed that students taught using zoom in instructional delivery performed better than the nonexperimental/control group taught using conventional teaching method. The test of hypothesis also showed that the difference in their academic performance was statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that there was a significance difference between the mean scores of students taught using zoom in instructional delivery and the nonexperimental/control group taught using conventional teaching method. The finding corroborates with Elenwo and Oteyi (2024) who found no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female students on the extent to which lecturers' utilization of audio tapes, internet, and electronic books in instructional delivery influence students' academic performance.

The data presented Table 4 determined the difference in the academic performance of undergraduate Educational Management students in Rivers State universities taught using computer networks in instructional delivery and the nonexperimental/control group taught using conventional teaching method. The finding revealed that students taught using computer networks in instructional delivery performed better than the nonexperimental/control group taught using conventional teaching method. The test of hypothesis also showed that the difference in their academic performance was statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that there was a significance difference between the mean scores of students taught using computer networks in instructional delivery and the nonexperimental/control group taught using conventional teaching method. The finding agrees with

Fajola (2012) who asserted that internet platforms perform multi-functional roles in teaching processes at all levels which in turn influences teaching effectiveness and academic performance of students.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that utilization of electronic instructional media such as zoom, and computer networks influenced students' academic performance in Rivers State universities. There is, therefore, no significant difference in the mean responses of RSU and IAUoE undergraduate Educational Management students on the influence of utilization of zoom and computer networks in instructional delivery on undergraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Seminars and training workshops be regularly organized to empower the teachers with skills needed for using the zoom for instructional delivery in the learning process by the school management and relevant government authorities.
2. Individual teachers and students should be encouraged to purchase some computers that are within their reach for adequate computer networking during classroom instructions.

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Appendix

SECTION A: DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

Please kindly fill correctly the blank spaces and tick (✓) against the box provided.

Name of Institution: _____

Designation: Lecturer ()

SECTION B: QUESTIONNAIRE ITEMS

Please kindly tick (✓) against the appropriate option (VHE = Very High Extent, HE = High Extent, LE = Low Extent, and VLE = Very Low Extent) that corresponds with your viewpoint.

S/ N	ITEMS	RESPONSE OPTIONS			
		VHE	HE	LE	VLE
	Extent of Lecturers' Utilization of Zoom as Electronic Instructional Media on Students' Academic Performance				
1.	The use of zoom helps students to stay on track in acquiring knowledge even when they are not physically present with their lecturers.				
2.	The use of zoom allows students to ask important questions as they collaborate on projects.				
3.	The use of zoom enhances the transmission of information among students and between lecturers and students for effective performance.				
4.	The use of zoom stimulates students' motivation and engagement in discussions for knowledge exchange.				
5.	The use of zoom helps to develop the general language learning of students in the teaching-learning process.				
6.	The use of zoom enhances the critical thinking skills of students as they participated within the instructional process.				
7.	The use of zoom improves the problem-solving skills of students as they interact with one another in the teaching-learning process.				
8.	The use of zoom facilitates students' acquisition of syntactic and semantic cognition with respect to sentences through the process of writing.				
9.	Using zoom sessions positively contributes to enhancing students learning in a creative and effective manner.				
10.	The use of zoom helps the teachers and students to get acquainted with innovations of teaching and learning in the 21 st century				
	Extent of Lecturers' Utilization of Google Classroom as Electronic Instructional Media on Students' Academic Performance				
11.	The use of google classroom allows the creation of classrooms which serves as a means of distributing tasks to students and submission of assignments which enhances their performance.				
12.	The use of google classroom promotes interaction among students for effective performances.				
13.	The use of google classroom gives students the opportunity to provide feedback and get direct input from classmates if they need help when finding difficulty to understand a task that they want to learn more about.				
14.	The use of google classroom helps students to communicate and discuss with their lecturer according to the learning schedule given by the lecturer.				
15.	The use of google classroom provides students with exposure to an online learning system which enhances their academic performance.				
16.	The use of google classroom enable students to access missed work due to absences and locate other learning resources they may need for acquiring knowledge.				
17.	The use of google classroom gives students the opportunity to obtain timely updates related to their lessons so that they can understand better the materials that improves their knowledge.				
18.	The use of google classroom promotes students' understanding of course content and interest in teaching and learning.				

19.	The use of google classroom enables lecturers to send mails to the students for their usage which enhances their performance academically.				
20	The use of google classroom expands the knowledge of lecturers and students				
	Extent of Lecturers' Utilization of WhatsApp as Electronic Instructional Media on Students' Academic Performance				
21.	The use of WhatsApp enhances interaction between students on personal, school, and course related topics which increases their learning.				
22.	The use of WhatsApp creates a sense of belonging in students which enhances their academic performance.				
23.	The use of WhatsApp eliminates social barriers and increases students' motivation in the teaching-learning process.				
24.	The use of WhatsApp enables students to access learning materials at any point in time which enhances their academic performance.				
25.	The use of WhatsApp helps to develop a constructive environment for students to learn and improve their performance.				
26.	The use of WhatsApp enables students to share information among them which enhances their academic performance.				
27.	The images used to support the text in WhatsApp helps for better understanding of various topics learnt by students.				
28	The use of WhatsApp enables students to develop the skills and attitude needed for effective use of ICTs for the enhancement of their academic performance.				
28.	The use of WhatsApp provides higher interactive potential for students to develop their intellectual and creative ability.				
29.	The use of WhatsApp develops students' skills in reading for effective academic performance.				
30.	The use of WhatsApp enables students have access to academic based resources during class which enhances their academic performance.				
	Extent of Lecturers' Utilization of Digital Textbooks as Electronic Instructional Media on Students' Academic Performance				
31.	The use of digital textbooks enables students to look up for information that supplements or contributes to classroom learning which improves their performance.				
32.	The use of digital textbooks improves students' collaboration and instant messaging to peers about concepts covered in class which enhances their academic performance.				
33.	The use of computer digital textbooks students' engagement in higher levels of processing problems that lead to deeper students learning.				
34.	The use of digital textbooks influences students to explore and generate retentive and self-learning which improves their performance.				
35.	The use of digital textbooks influences students to learn at their own pace for effective performance.				
36.	The use of digital textbooks allows students' control over the rate and sequence of their learning which improves their academic performance				
37	The use of digital textbooks encourages students' engagement in the teaching-learning process, and this enhances their academic performance.				
38.	The use of digital textbooks makes learning concrete and more lasting for the students which enhance their academic performance.				
39.	The use of digital textbooks helps to capture students' interest which eliminates boredom and boost clarity of concepts presented.				
40.	The use of digital textbooks makes lesson more practical and understandable for students' effective performance.				
	Extent of Lecturers' Utilization of Open Education Resources as Electronic Instructional Media on Students' Academic Performance				
41.	The use of open educational resources enables students to participate more actively in the class which enhances their academic performance.				
42.	The use of open education resources makes lecturers to deliver their lessons effectively for students' performance.				
43.	The use of open education resources contributes to the development of autonomous learning and higher order thinking skills among students.				

44.	The use of open education resources promotes students' reading skills by offering a larger variety of resources to supplement what has been taught.				
45.	The use of open education resources enables lecturers to properly prepare for lectures in an effort to provide effective teaching for the enhancement of students' academic performance.				
46.	The use of open education resources enhances students' motivation to learn and raises their level of concentration.				
47.	The use of open education resources aids students' perception and memory of information or knowledge.				
48.	The use open educational resources enables students to get informed on information that may not have been gotten on print material which enhances their academic performance.				
49.	The use of open educational resources provides students the freedom to follow their interest while still adhering to the requirements of the curriculum.				
50.	Usage of open educational resources facilitate collaboration and knowledge sharing for better academic performance				
	Extent of Lecturers' Utilization of Computer Networks as Electronic Instructional Media on Students' Academic Performance				
51.	The use of computer networks enable students to develop the skills and attitude needed for effective use of ICTs for the enhancement of their academic performance.				
52.	The use of computer networks develops students' skills in reading for effective academic performance.				
53.	The use of computer networks provides higher interactive potential for students to develop their intellectual and creative ability.				
54.	The uses of computer networks enable students have access to academic based resources during class which enhances their academic performance.				
55.	The use of computer networks enables students to look up for information that supplements or contributes to classroom learning which improves their performance.				
56.	The use of computer networks improves students' collaboration and instant messaging to peers about concepts covered in class which enhances their academic performance.				
57.	The use of computer networks supports students' engagement in higher levels of processing problems that lead to deeper students learning.				
58.	The use of computer networks influences students to explore and generate retentive and self-learning which improves their performance.				
59.	The use of computer networks influences students to learn at their own pace for effective performance.				
60.	The use of computer networks allows students' control over the rate and sequence of their learning which improves their academic performance				

The researcher developed two instruments each for research questions 1-6 having 30 multiple choice questions each with option A-D for the study. These instruments were Utilization of Electronic Instructional Media Achievement Test (UEIMAT) and Undergraduate Educational Management Students Achievement Test (UEMSAT) which were used to determine influence of utilization of electronic instructional media on undergraduate educational management students' academic performance in Rivers State Universities.

